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INTERNATIONAL PROTECTION OF ADULTS: FROM CATERPILLAR TO BUTTERFLY?!

Abstract: *Within the last few decades age pyramid has (undoubtedly) turned upside down. Instead of becoming younger society is growing older. Intertwined with increasing globalization and mobility, ageing society requires significant transformations in almost all sectors of society, particularly with regard to social protection. Due to freedom of movement of persons within the European Union, but also globally, international protection of vulnerable adults is certainly gaining its momentum. All the more so because currently, neither at the EU level, nor at the global level, there is a generally or at least widely accepted private international law regime for the international protection of vulnerable adults. The Hague Convention on International protection of Adults, which entered into force in 2009, is currently in force in only 15 states (out of which 12 Member States). Since it is impossible to ascertain exact reasons for the lack of ratifications, and having in mind several gaps which need to be mitigated in order to enhance legal certainty, one of the possible steps forward is to enact EU legislation to improve further the protection of vulnerable adults among member states, based on the HAPC. On that track, Proposal was presented in May 2023. The aim of this article is to establish whether this Proposal delivers what is promised, i.e. complete, simplified and more efficient international protection of vulnerable adults.*

Keywords: *international protection of adults, Hague 2000 Convention, Proposal for Regulation, human rights.*

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1. Introduction

Within the last few decades society is growing older. Consequently, there are more and more adults in need of protection. Based on limited data available, in between 2015 and 2020 there was an overall increase of 18% in the number of protective measures adopted across eight Member States.¹ „At the same time, NGO’s and medical/social care organizations have perceived and increase in the number of persons in need of protective measures and an increase in their cross-border mobility.“² Based on over 70% of the legal practitioner respondents, difficulties they face with regard to cross-border protection of adults refer to: language barriers and uncertainty regarding the validity of legal documents, legal uncertainty and varying rights from one Member State to another, difficulties in identifying which country has jurisdiction, lengthy legal proceedings and the non-recognition of foreign protective measures, (non)availability of legal aid to meet the costs of legal representation abroad, etc.³ All this difficulties directly impact legal certainty and diminish the advantages of international mobility of adults.⁴

Although there is a *lacuna* in addressing the problems of adults (especially elderly) as a group, it does not mean that they are not protected at all. Since the protection of vulnerable persons is regarded today as a human-rights concern,⁵ in 2006 United Nations introduced the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD),⁶ which is ratified by the EU and all of its Member States.⁷ Its purpose is to „promote, protect and ensure full and equal enjoyment of all human rights and fundamental freedoms by all

¹ Adriaenssens, L., Borrett, C., Fialon, S., Franzina, P., Rass-Masson, N., Sumner, I., *Study on the Cross-Border Legal Protection of Vulnerable Adults in the EU. Final Report*, European Commission, 2021., p. 12.

² *Ibidem*.

³ *Ibid.*, p. 13-14.

⁴ See: European Law Institute, *The Protection of Adults in International Situations. Report of the European Law Institute*, 2020, pp. 9-12. Retrieved January 12, 2024, from https://www.europeanlawinstitute.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/p_eli/Publications/ELI_Protection_of_Adults_in_International_Situations.pdf.

⁵ Franzina, P., Long, J., *The Protection of Vulnerable Adults in EU Member States. The added value of EU action in the light of The Hague Adults Convention*, Protection of Vulnerable Adults, European Added Value Assessment (ed. C. Salm), European Added Value Unit, 2016, p. 124.

⁶ The United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, Treaty Series 2515 (2006):3.

⁷ See: MacKay, D., *The United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities*, Syracuse Journal of International Law and Commerce, 34, 2007, pp. 323-331.

persons with disabilities, and to promote respect for their inherent dignity“⁸. However, only some of the EU Member States adapted their substantial law accordingly.

Same is happening with the only private international law instrument for the protection of the vulnerable adults–Hague Convention on the International Protection of Adults (CIPA),⁹ which was designated to protect vulnerable adults when in cross-border situations, which has been ratified by a very few states (among them only 12 member states). Instead, majority of states, including a number of EU Member States still rely on their own legal framework, with differing tools for the protection of vulnerable adults.

Due to the small number of ratifications, limited practical effects and the paradigm shift from traditional paternalistic approach to supported decision making, Commission proposed the adoption of new legislation¹⁰ with the aim of improving the operation of CIPA between Member States as well as harmonizing the CIPA’s solutions with the obligations under the CRPD.

This article consists of two parts. The first part will include an analysis of the CIPA’s framework, while the other will be focused on the Commission’s proposal. The hypothesis of this article is that even though the Commission’s Proposal brings many improvements, and certainly unveils „a butterfly“ for vulnerable adults, without systematic protection of all elderly adults as a group we are only half way through.

2. From Caterpillar ...

So, what does the CIPA offer? According to the Preamble of the HAPC, respect for the „dignity“ and „autonomy“ of vulnerable adults „are to be primary considerations“. Thus, the preservation and enhancement of existing freedoms and capacity of the vulnerable adult is a guiding principle of the whole text. It provides for „the protection in international situations of adults who, by reason of an impairment or insufficiency of their personal faculties, are not in a position to protect their interests“.¹¹ As any other private international law instrument, it determines the state whose authorities have

⁸ Article 1. of the CRPD.

⁹ Convention of 13 January 2000 on the International Protection of Adults. Retrieved February 21, 2024, from <https://assets.hcch.net/docs/c2b94b6b-c54e-4886-ae9f-c5bbef93b8f3.pdf>.

¹⁰ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on jurisdiction, applicable law, recognition and enforcement of measures and cooperation in matters relating to the protection of adults, COM(2023) 280 final, Brussels, 2 June 2023.

¹¹ Art. 1. of the CIPA.

jurisdiction to take measures directed to the protection of the persons or property of the adult, which law is to be applied by such authorities in exercising their jurisdiction and the conditions for recognition and enforcement of such measures of protection in all contracting states.¹² Finally, it establishes cooperation between authorities of the contracting states in order to facilitate operation of the Convention.

Dealing with cross-border cases, CIPA shows a great potential of upholding the interests of incapacitated adults across the globe.¹³ However, due to the modest number of ratifications it remains more of a potential than reality.¹⁴ Thus, despite the fact that different CIPA's provisions leave room for the interaction between Contracting and Non-member States,¹⁵ the picture remains globally unsatisfactory.¹⁶

Since the aim of this article is to establish whether the Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on jurisdiction, applicable law, recognition and enforcement of measures and cooperation in matters relating to the protection of adults¹⁷ delivers what is promised (i.e. complete, simplified and more efficient international protection of vulnerable adults), non-disputable content of the Convention will be left out and the focus will be put on the challenges in application of the Convention and the weaknesses of the Convention.

2.1. Challenges in the application of the Convention

The first challenge relates to para. 1. of art. 1 which clearly, although not expressly refers to vulnerability. Instead, it speaks of (permanent or temporary)¹⁸ „impairment or insufficiency of personal faculties“ of the adult

¹² See: Clive, E., *The New Hague Convention on the Protection of Adults*, Yearbook of Private International Law, 2, 2000, pp. 1-23, Frimston, R. Ruck Keene, A., van Overdijk, C., Ward, A.D., *The International protection of Adults*, Oxford University Press, 2015.

¹³ Bumbaca, V., *The Hague Convention on the protection of adults – plea for and practice of an „adult“ approach*, Yearbook of Private International Law (eds. A. Bonomi, I. Pretelli, G.P. Romano), Lausanne: Verlag Dr.Otto Schmidt and Swiss Institute of Comparative Law, 23, 2021/2022, p. 365.

¹⁴ Long J., *Rethinking Vulnerable Adults' Protection in the light of the 2000 Hague Convention*, International Journal of Law, Policy and Family, 27 (1), 2013, p. 52.

¹⁵ Art. 15 paras. 1-2, art. 18 in relation with art. 15 and art. 19 in relation to art. 13 para. 2.

¹⁶ Frimston, R., *The 2000 Adult Protection Convention – sleeping beauty or too complex to implement?*, The Elgar Companion to the Hague Conference on private International Law (eds. T. John, R. Gulati, B. Köhler), Edward Elgar Publishing, 2020, p. 226.

¹⁷ *Op. cit.*, note 10.

¹⁸ Lagarde, P., *Report of the Special Commission*, Proceedings of the Eighteenth Session 30

and, consequently „not being in a position to protect (his or her) interest“. According to the Explanatory report, „the adults whom the Convention is meant to protect are the physically or mentally incapacitated,¹⁹ who are suffering from an „insufficiency“ of their personal faculties, as well as persons usually elderly, suffering from an impairment of the same faculties, in particular suffering from Alzheimer’s disease“.²⁰ Emphasis on „personal faculties“ clearly shows that the intention of the legislator was to exclude protection in cases caused by external factors which require public/police measures of protection. However, from the wording of the Convention, it is not clear does it include cases which (in certain jurisdictions) in itself may be a cause of legal incapacity, like prodigality or drug addiction, gambling addiction, social isolation and illiteracy and other forms of inability to protect its own interests,²¹ which do not necessarily imply medical condition nor coincide with incapacitation. According to Lagarde Report, „the impairment or insufficiency of the adult’s faculties should arise from a „disease“, thus all this other cases are excluded.²²

Second challenge is the question of „capacity“. Although the Convention avoids using the term „capacity“, in many countries the imposition of protective measures is conditional upon incapacitation. Judging by the available protection measures (and the fact that not all of them are conditioned by incapacitation),²³ there is no symmetry between the protection of the vulnerable adult and his or her incapacitation.²⁴ In other words, the protection of vulnerable adult does not necessarily imply the limitation of his or her legal capacity.²⁵ However, it is only a part of explanation why the legislator avoided use of the term „adult with incapacity“ or „incapacitated adult“ and used the factual description instead. The other part is the fact that the

September to 19 October 1996 (ed. The Permanent Bureau of the HCCH), The Hague: SDU, 2, 1998, para. 9.

¹⁹ Although there were opinions that the Convention should only cover „those who lack decision-making capacity“. Such opinions are grounded in common law, where protective measures are available only for those who lack capacity. Lagarde, P., Explanatory Report for the Convention on the International Protection of Adults, The Hague: Hague Conference on Private International Law, 2017, p. 44.

²⁰ Lagarde (2017), *op. cit.*, p. 44.

²¹ Long (2013), *op. cit.*, pp. 63-64.

²² Lagarde (1998), *op. cit.*, para. 9.

²³ See art. 3 of the CIPA.

²⁴ Long (2013), *op. cit.*, p. 64, Salm, C., *Protection of Vulnerable Adults*, European Added Value Assessment, European Added Value Unit, 2016, p. 50.

²⁵ Long (2013), *op. cit.*, p. 64.

term „capacity“ may have different meaning. It may imply legal capacity (the ability to bear and exercise rights equally with other adults) but also mental capacity (decision-making skills of the individual in question).²⁶ Given that many legal systems have moved from status-based approach to functional approach to capacity, even in cases in which capacity may be affected person can still remain full legal personality in other areas.²⁷ Thus, person will be deprived of the legal capacity in respect of certain decisions while in all the other areas will be treated as legally capable.

Next challenge is use of the syntagma „interests of the adult“. This fraze is used scarcely in the Convention,²⁸ although, according to the text of the preamble „affirming the interests of the adult and respect for his or her dignity and autonomy are to be primary considerations“. It is obvious that, unlike the 1996 Hague Convention,²⁹ CIPA has not opted for the „best interests of the adult“, since „according to the Drafting Committee, the reference to the „best“ interests of the vulnerable adult did „not add much of substance to the text“ and „could be awkward in the event of the conflict between the interests which are equally respectable and best“.³⁰ Some argued that it is because in case of children the interests of children should prevail over the competing interests of their parents, while there is no such competition in case of vulnerable adults.³¹ And yet, the principle of the „best interests“ of the vulnerable adult is implemented in many national laws.³² In any case, when deciding on the interests of the adult the decision-maker is expected to think what is the best cause of action for that particular adult (a patient-centered

²⁶ Frimston (2020), *op. cit.*, p. 227. Also: UN Committee on Rights of Persons with Disabilities, General Comment No. 1 - Article 12: Equal recognition before the law, 2014.

²⁷ Frimston (2020), *op. cit.*, p. 228.

²⁸ In its preamble, art. 1 para. 1, 7 para. 1, art. 8 para. 1 and art. 15 para. 1.

²⁹ Convention on 19 October 1996 on Jurisdiction, Applicable Law, Recognition, Enforcement and Co-operation in Respect of Parental responsibility and Measures for the Protection of Children. Retrieved February 21, 2024, from <https://assets.hcch.net/docs/f16ebd3d-f398-4891-bf47-110866e171d4.pdf>.

³⁰ Long (2013), *op. cit.*, p. 58.

³¹ *Ibid.*, p. 59.

³² In some of them (e.g. England and Wales) there is even a statutory checklist for the determination of the best interests of the adult. See: Joyce, T., *Best Interests. Guidance on determining the best interests of adults who lack capacity to make a decision (or decisions) for themselves (England and Wales)*, Leicester: The British Psychological Society, 2007. Dunn, M.C., Clare, I.C.H., Holland, A.J., Gunn, M.J., *Constructing and reconstructing „best interests“: An interpretative examination of substitute decision-making under the Mental Capacity Act 2005*, *Journal of Social and Welfare Family Law*, 29 (2), 2007. Retrieved January 12, 2024, from <https://doi:10.1080/09649060701666598>.

approach), although the decision-making in different legal systems may take different paths. If the determination is based on the „best interests of the adult“, than it is more probable that the inspiration is taken from the determination of the best interests of the child,³³ in which case the determination includes „both the current and future interests of the adult, weighing them up and deciding which course of action is, on balance, the best course of action for that particular adult“. ³⁴ Such analysis relies predominantly on objective factors. If the determination is based on substituted decision-making,³⁵ than the decision-maker, basically, „tries to make a choice that the person themselves would have made, if they had the capacity to do so“. ³⁶ Thus, the subjective factors prevail. However, in most cases it is very difficult to draw a clear line between the two.³⁷

One of the often-raised challenges is the determination of habitual residence of the adult. Despite being a part of the Hague system since its introduction as a subsidiary criterion, in 1905,³⁸ it still poses problems. On one side, „it is attractive exactly due to the fact that it is not a rigid, legal concept, but instead a flexible factual concept that provides for flexibility and thus caters for every situation“. ³⁹ On the other side, „its content still causes doubts and tends to vary depending on the situation and factual circumstances at hand.“ ⁴⁰ Some are worried that the concept might not be entirely appropriate for the incapacitated adults (e.g. coma patient), since it is not clear whether the „habit“ in habitual implies some awareness by the person of his surroundings, or whether the „habit“ may be on the part of other persons who regu-

³³ See: Medić, I., *Najbolji interes djeteta u europskim prekograničnim predmetima*, Prekogranično kretanje djece u Europskoj uniji (ed. M. Župan), Osijek: Pravni fakultet, 2019, pp. 9-60.

³⁴ Joyce (2007), *op. cit.*, p. 7.

³⁵ *Ibid.*, p. 7 - „The use of substituted judgment as a framework for decision-making could, potentially, also lead to abuse. It makes it possible for a decision-maker to state that the wishes or preferences they are expressing are those of the person who lacks capacity, whereas they might, in fact, be the views of the decision-maker instead.“

³⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 7.

³⁷ Birchley, G., *The theoretisation of „best interests“ in bioethical accounts of decision-making*, BMC Medical Ethics, 22 (68), 2021. Retrieved January 12, 2024, from <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12910-021-00636-0>.

³⁸ Long (2013), *op. cit.*, p. 65.

³⁹ Curry-Sumner, I., *Vulnerable Adults in Europe. European added value of an EU legal instrument on the protection of vulnerable adults*, Protection of Vulnerable Adults, European Added Value Assessment (ed. C. Salm), European Added Value Unit, 2016, p. 63.

⁴⁰ Limante, A., *Establishing habitual residence of adults under the Brussels II a regulation: best practices from national case-law*, Journal of Private International Law, 14 (1), 2018, p. 161.

larly see him lying in one place.⁴¹ Despite some proposals for a definition in a future European instrument,⁴² it is not likely to happen. Although, so far, the European Court of Justice (ECJ) has been focused mainly on the clarification of the possible criteria for the determination of the habitual residence of the child,⁴³ there are more and more frequent clarifying interventions regarding the notion of habitual residence of the adult.⁴⁴ And these clarifications will have to suffice.⁴⁵ According to the recent judgements, nature of the habitual residence remains „functional“, and as such „allows the valorisation of all the factual and of intentional elements characterising a complex situation in order to adapt such a notion to the specific legal context and scope of the act in which it is inserted“.⁴⁶ Implementing a quantitative or qualitative definition to the concept in the Convention would challenge its interpretation in the various other Conventions (and Regulations)⁴⁷ in which it is used.⁴⁸ Also, practice shows that the number of difficult cases is rather limited and that courts and other authorities are becoming more familiar with the concept.⁴⁹

Ex lege power of representation is not explicitly addressed, since it is not a measure of protection⁵⁰ and it hasn't been granted by the adult. However,

⁴¹ Ruck Keene, A., *Part II, The cross-border protection of adults: Hague 35*, The International Protection of Adults (eds. R. Frimston, A. Ruck Keene, C. van Overdijk, A.D. Ward), Oxford University Press, 2015, p. 111-118.

⁴² *Ibid.*

⁴³ C-523/07 *Applicant A*, ECLI:EU:C:2009:225; C-497/10 *PPU Mercredi v. Chaffe*, ECLI:EU:C:2010:829; C-376/14 *PPU C v. M*, ECLI:EU:C:2014:2268, C-499/15 *W and V v. X*, ECLI:EU:C:2017:118, C-111/17 *PPU OL v. PQ*, ECLI:EU:C:2017:436, C-512/17 *HR*, ECLI:EU:C:2018:513; C-393/18 *PPU UD v. XB*, ECLI:EU:C:2018:835.

⁴⁴ Case 452/93P *Pedro Magdalena Fernández v. Commission of the European Communities*, ECLI:EU:C:1994:332, C-90/97 *Swaddling v. Adjudication Officer*, ECLI:EU:C:1999:96, C-168/08 *Laszlo Hadadi v. Csilla Marta Mesko*, ECLI:EU:C:2009:474, C-289/201B *v. FA*, ECLI:EU:C:2021:561, C-462/22BM *v. LO*, ECLI:EU:C:2023:553.

⁴⁵ For a Guidelines, see: Schuz, R., *Habitual Residence: Review of Developments and Proposed Guidelines*, *Laws*, 12 (62). Retrieved January 12, 2024, from <https://doi.org/10.3390/laws12040062>. Boiché, A., *A Spouse Can Only Have One Habitual Residence for the Application of Article 3 Brussels II-bis*, *European Forum*, 6 (3), 2021, pp. 1339-1343.

⁴⁶ Ricci, C., *Habitual Residence as a Ground of Jurisdiction in Matrimonial Disputes Connected with the EU: Challenges and Potential*, *Civil Procedure Review*, 11 (1), 2020, 175.

⁴⁷ Added by the author.

⁴⁸ Curry-Sumner (2016), *op. cit.*, p. 63 and Lagarde (2017), *op. cit.*, p. 56.

⁴⁹ Franzina, Long (2016), *op. cit.*, p. 159.

⁵⁰ Surveys show that protection by operation of law is available only in seven Member States and in three of these States it covers more or less the same scope as other types of representation. See: Adriaenssens *et al.* (2021), *op. cit.* p. 11.

it does not mean that it left out of the scope of the Convention and, consequently, Proposal for Regulation.⁵¹ Competent authorities of the Contracting State may, in cooperation between the authorities of Contracting Parties, give effect to *ex lege* representation in accordance with their own law.⁵²

2.2. Weaknesses of the Convention

Based on the case law of the Contracting States, several weaknesses of the HACP have been identified. In this text, they will be addressed in line with their appearance in the Convention.

The first (and maybe the most obvious) weakness is limited geographical scope. With regard to jurisdiction, it means that the Convention applies only to adults which are habitually resident at the territory of Contracting State. In cases where the adult concerned does not have habitual residence in a Member State, it leaves some room for the application of national rules on international jurisdiction.⁵³ Although such approach is common for the Hague Convention, it is not in line with the recent EU trends.⁵⁴ With regard to recognition and enforcement, both are based on the principle of reciprocity, providing for recognition and enforcement of measures taken in Contracting States only. It means that prior to the ratification of the Convention by all Member States two tracks of recognition and enforcement within the EU will remain.

Next weakness is related to jurisdiction. Convention attributes primary jurisdiction (to take protective measures) to „the judicial or administrative authorities of the Contracting State of the habitual residence of the adult“,⁵⁵ which jurisdiction changes in case of a change of the adult's habitual residence.⁵⁶ Thus, the shift of jurisdiction is immediate, which may cause difficulties in some cases, for example, in case of an adult who retains a good degree of autonomy which allows him to move freely. It may happen that the adult

⁵¹ More about this topic see in: European Association of Private International Law (EAPIL), *Position paper in response to the European Commission's public consultation on an EU-wide protection for vulnerable adults*, 2022. Retrieved March 5, 2024, from <https://eapil.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/Position-Paper-29.03.22.pdf>.

⁵² Conclusions and Recommendations of the Special Commission (SC) on the practical operation of the Convention of 13 January 2000 on the International Protection of Adults, 15 November 2022, p. 5. Retrieved January 12, 2024, from <https://assets.hcch.net/docs/06db03d0-812c-42fb-b76d-4e6e05a91b3b.pdf>.

⁵³ Curry-Sumner (2016), *op. cit.*, p. 60.

⁵⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 59-60.

⁵⁵ Art. 5 para. 1 of the CIPA.

⁵⁶ Art. 5 para. 2 of the CIPA.

exercised his free movement rights without the knowledge of his guardian. According to art. 12 of the CIPA „measures taken in application of articles 5 to 9 remain in force according to their terms, even if a change of circumstances has eliminated the basis upon which jurisdiction was founded, so long as the authorities which have jurisdiction under the Convention have not modified, replaced or terminated such measures“. Consequently, if (due to change of circumstances) modification of the protection measure is needed, the lack of rules providing for the continuing jurisdiction of the authorities of the state of former habitual residence of the adult leaves the guardian with one option only - to seek protection of the adult from the authorities of the Contracting State of the adult's new habitual residence. Since they will need some time to make an informed decision, this may result in a temporary gap in the protection of the adult.

Also, although the Preamble emphasizes autonomy of the adult as a primary consideration, such claim it is rather difficult to accepting relation to jurisdiction. According to art. 8 para. 2(d) of the Convention, adult is given the possibility to choose (in writing) the State whose authorities will take measures directed at his protection. However, „the authorities chosen by the adult to take protective measures in the event of his or her incapacity cannot claim jurisdiction merely on the ground of that choice“. ⁵⁷ They may acquire jurisdiction only upon a request of the state having jurisdiction for the merits of the case or on an application by the authority of another Contracting State, which is conditioned by their assessment of the interests of the adult. ⁵⁸ In relation to art. 16 of the Convention, the absence of any possibility for an adult to choose in advance the state whose authorities should have jurisdiction over his or her protection leads to the divergence between *forum* and *ius* in case of granted powers of representation. It may be mitigated by reference to para. 2 of art. 15 but it is dependent on the discretion of the competent authority, thus running counter predictability requirement.

Next weakness is the enforcement of foreign protective measures. It may be difficult due to the weakness for the provision of evidence abroad of the powers granted to a representative of a vulnerable adult. According to art. 38, CIPA does establish a certificate designed to prove representative's capacity but practice shows that they are rarely issued. ⁵⁹ Also, contrary to contemporary trends which imply automatic enforceability and procedural rules for enforcement, according to art. 25 of the CIPA measures taken and

⁵⁷ Franzina, Long (2016), *op. cit.*, p. 161.

⁵⁸ Art. 8. par. 1. of the CIPA.

⁵⁹ Franzina, Long (2016), *op. cit.*, p. 161.

enforceable in one Contracting State will⁶⁰ be declared enforceable or registered for the purpose of enforcement in other Contracting State, according to the procedure provided in that State. National procedures vary, not only in content but also in length, and may result in a temporary gap in the protection of the adult.

Final identified weakness is poor cooperation and communication among the authorities of the Contracting States.⁶¹ According to the provisions of Chapter V of the CIPA, cooperation is channeled mostly through the Central authorities in the Contracting States, in a very light manner.⁶² Direct communication is not envisaged although, in the meantime, it has become a standard in family matters,⁶³ which protection of vulnerable adults *de facto* often turns out to be.⁶⁴ In order to make it more efficient, direct judicial communication should be made a standard with regard to the proceedings, while indirect communication *via* Central Authorities should be used as assistance.

Last but not least, absence of a supranational court which would be authorized to interpret the Hague conventions leads to differing results in interpretation of CIPA provisions across the Contracting States and, consequently, decrease in legal certainty and deterring from free movement.

3. ... to Butterfly?!

Since the cross-border mobility of adults (including those who require support with decision-making) is growing by the day, and the EU cannot itself become a party to the CIPA (Arts. 53 and 54 make clear that the convention is only open to states),⁶⁵ one of the possible steps forward was to

⁶⁰ Upon request by an interested party.

⁶¹ Franzina, Long (2016), *op. cit.*, p. 148-157.

⁶² Art. 32 para. 1 of the CIPA: „When a measure of protection is contemplated, the competent authorities under the Convention, if the situation of the adult so requires, may request any authority of another Contracting State which has information relevant to the protection of the adult to communicate such information.“

⁶³ See: Hague Conference on Private International Law, Direct Judicial Communication, The Judges newsletter 15, 2009, p. 8. Kreeger, J. L., *The International Hague Judicial network – A Progressing Work*, Family Law Quarterly, 48 (2), 2014, pp. 221-234. Lortie, P., *Direct Judicial Communications and the International Hague Network of Judges under the Hague 1980 Child Abduction Convention*, Private International Law in the Jurisprudence of European Courts – Family at Focus (ed.M. Župan), Osijek: Faculty of Law, 2015, pp. 135-157.

⁶⁴ Either through ex-lege representation or powers of representation granted to the family member.

⁶⁵ Art. 53 para. 1 – „The Convention shall be open for signature by the States which were Members of the Hague Conference on Private International Law on 2 October 1999.“ Art. 54.

use its internal competencies (based on Art. 81 para.2 of the TFEU)⁶⁶ and to enact the EU legislation to improve further the protection of vulnerable adults among Member States, based on the CIPA. Since the Convention does not prevent Contracting States from furthering their cooperation,⁶⁷ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on jurisdiction, applicable law, recognition and enforcement of measures and cooperation in matters relating to the protection of adults was presented in May 2023.⁶⁸

3.1. Added value of the Proposal for a Regulation ... in matters relating to the protection of adults

So, in a nutshell, what this Proposal brings? As it has been explained in the Memorandum attached to the Proposal, „the added value of the proposed Regulation is simplification and modernization of the rules included in the Convention for the EU’s circumstances and the strengthening of cooperation among Member States in the area of the protection of adults“.⁶⁹ The Proposal aims to ensure consistency with the existing policy provisions in this area, as well as with other Union policies. Therefore, proposed Regula-

para. 1. – „Any other State may accede the Convention ...“.

⁶⁶ Art. 81 para. 2 TFEU – „For the purposes of paragraph 1, the European Parliament and the Council, acting in accordance with the ordinary legislative procedure, shall adopt measures, particularly when necessary for the proper functioning of the internal market, aimed at ensuring:

- (a) the mutual recognition and enforcement between member States of judgments and of decisions in extrajudicial cases;
- (b) the cross-border service of judicial and extrajudicial documents;
- (c) the compatibility of the rules applicable in the Member States concerning conflict of laws and of jurisdiction;
- (d) cooperation in taking of evidence;
- (e) effective acces to justice;
- (f) the elimination of obstacles to the proper functioning of civil proceedings, if necessary by promoting the compatibility of the rules on civil procedure applicable in the Member States;
- (g) the development of alternative methods of dispute settlement
- (h) support for the training of the judiciary and judicial staff.“

⁶⁷ Art. 49 of the CIPA – para. (2) „This Convention does not affect the possibility for one or more Contracting States to conclude agreements which contain, in respect of adults habitually resident in any of the State parties to such agreements, provisions on matters governed by this Convention.“; para. (3) „Agreements to be concluded by one or more Contracting States on matters within the scope of this Convention do not affect, in the relationship of such States with other Contracting States, the application of the provisions of this Convention.“.

⁶⁸ *Op. cit.*, note 10.

⁶⁹ COM(2023) 280 final, 31. 5. 2023., p. 2.

tion incorporates some rules from the CIPA and makes them directly applicable in relations between Member States. According to recital (10) of the Proposal, „the interpretation of the rules laid down in this Regulation should be guided by its objectives that are to enhance the protection of fundamental rights of adults in cross-border situations, including their right to autonomy, access to justice, right to property, right to be heard, right to free movement and equality“. In other words, Proposal is to be interpreted in line with the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR)⁷⁰ and, with regard to persons with disabilities, in line with the CRPD.

With regard to jurisdictional rules, Proposal relies on CIPA's rules on jurisdiction and the same rules apply to a case involving Member States and third countries that are Contracting Parties to the Convention. On top of that, Proposal adds a new jurisdictional ground. It allows for the choice of jurisdiction made by the adult,⁷¹ without the need for any further proceedings. However, exercise of such jurisdiction is made conditional upon three cumulative conditions: the state of mind of the adult at the time of the choice, interests of the adult and the authorities of the adult's habitual residence.⁷² Such solution leaves some room for the assessment whether a jurisdiction of a chosen court, at the time the court is seized, is still in the best interests of the adult.⁷³ It may be particularly useful if there is a big time-gap between the choice and seizing of the court and the situation of the adult is significantly altered. Although it may be inferred from para. 2 of art. 6, Proposal explicitly states that the jurisdiction of a chosen court is not exclusive, thus, it does not prevent authorities having jurisdiction under the CIPA to exercise

⁷⁰ Convention for the protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (1950). Retrieved March 10, 2024, from https://www.echr.col.int/documents/d/echr/convention_ENG.

⁷¹ Art. 6 of the Proposal. See: European Association of Private International Law (EAPIL), *Position paper in response to the European Commission's public consultation on an EU-wide protection for vulnerable adults*, 2022. Retrieved March 5, 2024, from <https://eapil.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/Position-Paper-29.03.22.pdf>.

⁷² Art. 6. para. 1 – „...the authorities of a Member State other than the Member State in which the adult is habitually resident shall have jurisdiction where all of the following conditions are met:

- (a) the adult chose the authorities of that member State, when he or she was still in a position to protect his or her interests;
- (b) that the exercise of jurisdiction is in the interest of the adult; and
- (a) that the authorities of the Member State having jurisdiction under the jurisdictional grounds set in CIPA (arts. 5 to 8) have not exercised their jurisdiction.

⁷³ Recital (20) of the Proposal.

their jurisdiction.⁷⁴ Thus, where the authorities of the habitual residence of the adult have already exercised their jurisdiction, the authorities designated through the choice of the adult should abstain from exercising their jurisdiction. Finally, since the Regulation complements CIPA, „the mechanisms established by the Convention giving priority to certain grounds of jurisdiction, limiting the effects of certain measures, and setting up exchange of information between the authorities of the habitual residence and the authorities with subsidiary or concurrent jurisdiction, should therefore also apply in the EU to authorities exercising their jurisdiction according to the choice made by the adult“.⁷⁵

With regard to the applicable law, Proposal fully incorporates the rules laid down by the CIPA. Art. 8 of the Proposal explicitly refers to the whole Chapter III of the Convention. However, as in the CIPA, there are no specific rules for ex-lege powers of representation. Also, advance medical directives which are not combined with the power of representation are neither covered by the CIPA nor by the Proposal.

With regard to recognition and enforcement, the recognition of measures taken in other Member States is also governed by the Proposal. It allows for simplified enforcement procedures within the EU, in a way that it abolishes the declaration of enforceability that is still required under the CIPA. List of grounds for refusing the recognition of a measure is exhaustive. Focal point, here as well, is „interest of the adult“ assessed through the human rights-based approach. When assessing whether a measure taken in another Member State is manifestly contrary to public policy, the authorities of a Member State where recognition is sought must take into account arts. 3, 9, 29 and 19 of the CRPD.⁷⁶ Also, the adult must have been given the „effective and genuine“ opportunity to express his or her views, except in cases of urgency or absolute inability to express his or her views.⁷⁷ Finally, as in parental responsibility cases,⁷⁸ later measure will prevail.

In line with other recent Regulations, Proposal also includes authentic

⁷⁴ Art. 7 of the Proposal.

⁷⁵ Recital (21) of the Proposal.

⁷⁶ Recital (15) of the Proposal.

⁷⁷ Recital (27) of the Proposal.

⁷⁸ See Art. 39 para 1(e) of the Council Regulation 2019/1111 of 25 June 2019 on jurisdiction, the recognition and enforcement of decisions in matrimonial matters and the matters of parental responsibility, and on international child abduction (recast), OJ L 178, 2. 7. 2019.

instruments⁷⁹ directed to the protection of adults.⁸⁰ They are supposed to have the same (or the most comparable) evidentiary effects in other Member States as they have in the the State of origin. In order to facilitate their circulation within the EU, they have to be attested, i. e. accompanied by a certificate from Annex II of the Proposal given by the competent authorities in the Member State of origin.

Also, the Proposal contains necessary rules on: cooperation between the Competent Authorities, establishment of the European Certificate of Representation, establishment and interconnection of protection registers, digital communication and data protection. They represent a major modernization compared to the older rules of the CIPA.

Main improvements with regard to cooperation include better regulation of the tasks of Central Authorities as well as of competent authorities. Proposal also envisages direct communication between competent authorities and associated forms (set out in Annex VIII) that facilitate this communication.⁸¹ Better communication and cooperation is envisaged also in connection with contemplated cross-border placement of the adult.⁸²

A major innovation is the introduction of a European Certificate of Representation which will supersede the certificate under the art. 38 of the CIPA.⁸³ The Certificate can be issued for use by representatives who, in

⁷⁹ See: Chapter VI of the Council Regulation (EC) No 4/2009 of 18 december 2008 on jurisdiction, applicable law, recognition and enforcement of decisions and cooperation in matters relating to maintenance obligations, OJ L 7, 10.1.2009., Chapter V of the Regulation (EU) No 650/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 July 2012 on jurisdiction, applicable law, recognition and enforcement of the authentic instruments in matters of succession and of the creation of a European Certificate of Succession, OJ L 107, 27. 7. 2012., Chapter IV of the Regulation (EU) No 1215/2012 of the European parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2012 on jurisdiction and the recognition and enforcement of judgments in civil and commercial matters (recast), OJ L 351, 20.12.2012., Chapter V of the Council Regulation (EU) 2016/1103 of 24 June 2016 implementing enhanced cooperation in the area of jurisdiction, applicable law and the recognition and enforcement of decisions in matters of matrimonial property regimes, OJ L 183, 8.7.2016., Chapter V of the Council Regulation (EU) 2016/1104 of 24 June 2016 implementing enhanced cooperation in the area of jurisdiction, applicable law and the recognition and enforcement of decisions in matters of the property consequences of registered partnerships, OJ L 183, 8.7.2016., Chapter IV-Section IV of the Council Regulation (EU) 2019/1111 of 25 June 2019 on jurisdiction, the recognition and enforcement of decisions in matrimonial matters and the matters of parental responsibility, and on international child abduction (recast), OJ L 178, 2.7.2019.

⁸⁰ Chapter V of the Proposal.

⁸¹ Art. 27 of the Proposal.

⁸² Art. 21 of the Proposal.

⁸³ Same as in Art. 62 para. 2 of the Regulation (EU) No 650/2012 of the European Parliament

another Member State, need to invoke their powers to represent a vulnerable adult. The issuing authority is the competent authority⁸⁴ or authority which has access to information on the source measure or the source powers of representation. Regime of the Certificate resembles the one already established for succession matters,⁸⁵ with the exception of the Register which is not envisaged for succession matters.

Finally, Proposal contains detailed rules on relation between the Proposal and the CIPA. With some exceptions (in order to ensure a smooth coordination with the Contracting States of the CIPA which are not Member States), the basic factor that triggers the application of the Proposal is the vulnerable adult's habitual residence in the territory of a Member State.

3.2. *Unmet expectations*

Apart from improvements, are there any unmet expectations in this Proposal? In short, yes. It is obvious that the Proposal addresses all the weaknesses displayed by the CIPA and brings it in line with recent private international law standards. However, it doesn't address any of the challenges: vulnerability, capacity, interests of the adult or determination of habitual residence. There were expectations that the Proposal might (or maybe should) explicitly address cases which (in certain jurisdictions) in itself may be a cause of legal incapacity (prodigality, drug addiction, gambling addiction, and other forms of inability to protect its own interests),⁸⁶ which do not necessarily imply medical condition nor coincide with incapacitation but, however, require some form of protection. Thus, it remains a matter of a national law.

The same with capacity, which proves to be a source of a huge dissatisfaction. Namely, the European Disability Forum,⁸⁷ as well as some other civil societies are putting the pressure on the Commission to amend the proposal in line with the content and wording of the CRPD in order to push forward those Member States which are still relying on the traditional protective or substitute decision making approach instead of the human rights or sup-

and of the Council of 4 July 2012 on jurisdiction, applicable law, recognition and enforcement of the authentic instruments in matters of succession and of the creation of a European Certificate of Succession, OJ L 107, 27. 7. 2012., issuance of this Certificate is not mandatory (Art. 34. para. 2 of the Proposal).

⁸⁴ The one that has taken the measure or confirmed powers of representation.

⁸⁵ Compare with Chapter VI of the Regulation 650/2012.

⁸⁶ Long (2013), *op. cit.*, pp. 63-64.

⁸⁷ European Disability Forum („EDF“), Re: Proposed EU Regulation on the protection of adults. Opinion, 2023. Retrieved January 15, 2024, from <https://www.edf-feph.org/content/uploads/2023/11/Legal-Opinion-Vulnerable-Adults.pdf>.

portive decision making approach. Their main concerns are: the recognition of deprivation of legal capacity across the Union, lack of explicit mention of the recognition of supported decision-making mechanisms and facilitated cross-border placement in institutions (particularly residential and psychiatric institutions).

Art. 12 of the CRPD stipulates that every person, regardless of their mental capacity, has legal capacity.⁸⁸ Although the Proposal expressly states in its recitals that „the interpretation of the rules laid down in Regulation should be „guided by its objectives that are to enhance the protection of fundamental rights and freedoms“⁸⁹ and that „rights safeguarded in the UNCRPD are to be protected both in national and cross-border cases“,⁹⁰ according to the released UN’s experts Opinion „the core of the proposed Regulation does not comply with the UNCRPD“.⁹¹ Therefore they require revisiting of certain articles of the Proposal, *in concreto* arts. 2, 3, 13 and 21 of the Proposal. Forceful elimination of guardianship or other forms of substitute decision from the text of the Convention in order to avoid legitimation of legal incapacitation, still present in many national laws, doesn’t seem to be the right path. It would mean departing from the principle of neutrality. Whether it is desirable or whether there is a real need for such an approach is debatable. It won’t speed up the process of substantial law changes at the Member States level but it might complicate things on the CIPA - Proposal level. Proposal is already advanced enough to allow the respect and advancement of human rights of vulnerable adults in international arena as well as organic growth of the CIPA in the same direction.⁹²

⁸⁸ On the conflicting interpretations of art. 12 of the CRPD, see: Stelma-Roorda, H.N., Blankman, C., Antokolskaia, A changing paradigm of protection of vulnerable adults and its implications for the Netherlands, *Family & Law*, February 2019. Retrieved February 2, 2024, from <https://DOI:10.5553/FenR/000037>.

⁸⁹ Recital (10) of the Proposal.

⁹⁰ *Ibid.*

⁹¹ Quinn, G., Mahler, C., Joint Submission from the UN Special Rapporteur on the rights of persons with disabilities (G. Quinn) and the Independent Expert on the enjoyment of all human rights by older persons (C. Mahler), 2023. Retrieved January 10, 2024, from <https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/documents/issues/disability/olderpersons/Annex-Joint-Submission-Towards-Greater-Coherence-International-Law.pdf>.

⁹² For other possible routes for managing overlapping Treaties see: Rolland, S.E., Ruck Keene, A., Study. Interpreting the 2000 Hague Convention on the International protection of Adults Consistently with the 2007 UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, 2021. Retrieved January 12, 2024, from https://www.ohchr.org/Documents/issues/Disability/hague-CRPD_Study.docx.

Finally, with regard to habitual residence, it would have been useful to have a guidance „how to deal with situation where the adult concerned is not free to leave the place where he or she is cared for, or the situation where the adult in question did not choose voluntarily to settle in the particular place where he or she lives“.⁹³ It could have been given through recitals, like in Succession Regulation.

4. Conclusion

One of the most important, and the most difficult, of the issues involved in adult protection matters is how to strike a balance between the right to personal autonomy, self-determination and protection. Even today, legal systems take very different approach from each other to promote the personal autonomy and self-determination of adults who do not have full decision-making capacity or (as a result of an impairment or insufficiency in their personal faculties) can no longer fully protect their interests. Nonetheless, we can observe a major paradigm shift, from paternalism and a substitute decision-making approach to autonomy and supportive decision-making human rights based approach.⁹⁴ Persons with impairments in decision-making capacity today are perceived as actors and recognized members of society, instead of as objects of protection.

When it comes to international protection of adults, the Convention on the International Protection of Adults (CIPA)⁹⁵ and the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD),⁹⁶ together with the EU's Proposal for a Regulation on jurisdiction, applicable law, recognition and enforcement of measures and cooperation in matters relating to the protection of the adults⁹⁷ „will ultimately result in a basic regime of universal character, coupled by a special regime that would improve the latter at a regional level“.⁹⁸

⁹³ European Law Institute, *The Protection of Adults in International Situations. Report of the European Law Institute*, 2022. Retrieved January 12, 2024, from https://www.europeanlawinstitute.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/p_eli/Publications/ELI_Protection_of_Adults_in_International_Situations.pdf.

⁹⁴ Stelma-Roorda, H.N., Blankman, C., Antokolskaia, A changing paradigm of protection of vulnerable adults and its implications for the Netherlands, *Family & Law*, February 2019. Retrieved February 2, 2024, from <https://DOI:10.5553/FenR/000037>.

⁹⁵ *Op. cit.*, note 9.

⁹⁶ *Op. cit.*, note 6.

⁹⁷ *Op. cit.*, note 10.

⁹⁸ European Association of Private International Law (EAPIL), *Position paper in response to the European Commission's public consultation on an EU-wide protection for vulnerable adults*, 2022. Retrieved March 5, 2024, from <https://eapil.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/>

They provide legal certainty and human rights-based approach with regard to jurisdiction, applicable law and recognition and enforcement of measures of protection of vulnerable adults taken in another Contracting/Member State. However, they all have their limitations. The most obvious one is their personal scope of application, limited in a way that covers only the most vulnerable among the adults.

There is still a huge void in the (national and international) protection of adults in general, in particular those adults who (still) don't need protection due to vulnerability (as determined by the CIPA) but may (and often do) need it for other reasons (e.g. age). Despite the fact that parts of the world are progressively ageing (in particular, the Northern hemisphere elder law has attracted little attention, almost to the point of neglect.⁹⁹ On one side, it may be due to plurality of concepts regarding the old age (chronological, social and physiological)¹⁰⁰ but, on the other side it may be due to the fact that government institutions have not yet adapted to the shift in the age distribution of the population.¹⁰¹ To this day, „the UN Principles and the General Comment on the Economic, Social and Cultural Rights of Older Persons¹⁰² constitute the only internationally agreed human rights instrument addressing the needs of all older people“.¹⁰³ Even the text of the ECHR,¹⁰⁴ does not contain any explicit reference to „older persons“. Thus, age in itself does not justify any special status of older persons in the proceedings before the ECtHR, although the Court takes into account elderly's „limited physical mobility, decreased information processing and problem-solving skills that are often

Position-Paper-29.03.22.pdf .

⁹⁹ Doron, I.: *From National to International Elder Law*, *The Journal of international Ageing, Law & Policy*, 1 (43), 2005, p. 44.

¹⁰⁰ Social being the most important one. More about the construction of ageing as a social problem see in: Fredvang, M., Biggs, S., *The rights of older persons. Protection and gaps under human rights law*, Brotherhood of St Laurence and University of Melbourne Centre for Public Policy, Melbourne, 2012, pp. 6-7.

¹⁰¹ Henschuan, S., Rodríguez-Piñero, L., *Ageing and the protection of human rights: current situation and outlook*, Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC) – Project Document, 2011, p. 15.

¹⁰² General Comment No. 6 of the Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights of Older Persons (1995). Retrieved March 13, 2024, from <https://www.refworld.org/legal/general/cesr/1995/en/28739>.

¹⁰³ Doron, Mewhinney (2007), *op. cit.*, p. 7. For the non-binding instruments, see: Doron, I., Mewhinney, K. (eds.), *The Rights of Older Persons: Collection of International Documents*, International Federation of Ageing (IFA), Jerusalem, 2007.

¹⁰⁴ *Op. cit.*, note 70.

related to declining memory capacity and weakened evaluation skills¹⁰⁵ or, in other words, their vulnerability. However, derivative protection of elderly based on the rights enshrined in the ECHR does not allow the establishment of comprehensive age-specific standards that will lead to a better protection of all elderly at the national and international level. Thus, there is an urgent need for legally binding international instrument which will establish standards for the protection of their specific needs, as well. Only when this is achieved, we will be able to claim that we have a satisfactory system for the, national and international, protection of all adults.

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